

FREE EDGE DELAMINATION ONSET CRITERION

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SUMMARY : This paper shows the results of a theoretical and experimental study of the free edge delamination on carbon-epoxy laminates. Edge delamination tests have been made on different stacking sequences to make specimens delaminate under various modes (interlaminar tension, shear or combinations of the two). The tests give results which are necessary to validate a criterion. The thickness influence on the delamination onset stress is used to identify the parameter of the criterion. This method provides good results for the shear delamination. One set of parameters is sufficient to predict the onset delamination stress for $[\pm\theta]_s$, with $\theta = 10, 20$ and 30° .

KEYWORDS: LAMINATE, DELAMINATION ONSET, CRITERION, EDGE DELAMINATION TEST

INTRODUCTION

Various approaches have been investigated in order to predict delamination. Regarding to the propagation, energetic methods are often used. When studying the onset, stress criteria can be of great interest [1]. This is the approach chosen here. The calculations use an asymptotic method to provide interlaminar stresses. Based on CLT, it consists of a local correction of the plane stresses, which allows the boundary conditions to be correct on the edge of the laminate. The present study consists of a confrontation of a model with test results. The criterion parameters are identified by a least square method using test results and model predictions. Each term of the criterion is studied separately. Specific tests were made for this study.

TESTS

Different specimens were tested to validate the model. They are made of carbon-epoxy T800/914. The specimens have been cut with a diamond wheel. Their dimensions are 300×20 mm², with aluminium tabs.

fig 1 : edge delamination test

The mechanical properties of UD ply are given in table 1.

E_{xx} (Gpa)	E_{yy} (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	E_{zz} (GPa)	G_{xz} (GPa)	G_{yz} (GPa)	ν_{zx}	ν_{yz}
159	8,4	4,1	0,33	8,4	4,1	2,8	0,33	0,33
Identified figures					Extrapolated figures			

table 1 : T800/914 properties

Tests were lead at a speed of 0.5 mm/min until 80% of the delamination onset load, then it was dropped down to 0.05 mm/min to get more accuracy to detect the damage phenomenon.

laminate	Interface	Mode
$[\pm 10_n]_s$	+10/-10	shear
$[\pm 20_n]_s$	+20/-20	shear
$[\pm 30_n]_s$	+30/-30	shear
$[25_{2n}/-25_{2n}/90_n]_s$	inside the 90° ply	tension
$[15_{2n}/90_n/-15_{2n}]_s$	15/90	tension and shear
$[30_{2n}/90_n/-30_{2n}]_s$	30/90	tension and shear

table 2 : EDT specimen

The theoretical study of the criterion is based on thickness influence. For each specimen type, several thicknesses were tested (n=1 to 5, and 8 for $[\pm 10_n]_s$). Five specimens of each type and each thickness were tested.

An acoustic emission system was used to detect the first macroscopic damage. The information from AE were confirmed by enhanced Xray radiography.

- $[\pm\theta_n]_s$ $\theta=10, 20$ and 30°

These specimens were often used in previous works. They are known to delaminate in a unstable way. Here, some tests have been stopped after delamination onset and before whole failure. Figure 2 shows a $[\pm 30]_s$ specimen with a delamination at both $+30/-30$ interface.

figure 2 : edge of a delaminated $[\pm 30]_s$ specimen

figure 3 : X radiography of a delaminated $[\pm 30]_s$ specimen

When $\theta=30^\circ$, specimens exhibit a non linear behaviour.

- $[25_{2n}/-25_{2n}/90_n]_s$

Delamination of these laminates is stable (fig. 4).

figure 4 : edge of a delaminated $[\pm 25_2/90]_s$ specimen

figure 5 : X radiography of a delaminated $[\pm 25_2/90]_s$ specimen

- $[15_{2n}/90_n/-15_{2n}]_s$ and $[30_{2n}/90_n/-30_{2n}]_s$

Acoustic emission increases and some small cracks were observed with microscopy. However they were too small to be photographed : when polishing the edge to have a good surface, cracks vanish because of their very small depth. Fig. 6 shows what could be seen on the edge of a $[15_{2n}/90_n/-15_{2n}]_s$ laminate.

figure 6 : edge of a $[15_{2n}/90_n/-15_{2n}]_s$ specimen

It is difficult to know which crack, interlaminar or intralaminar (transverse cracks with an angle of 45°), occurs first and whether the interlaminar criterion is likely to predict this failure.

Results of the tests are summarised in table 2.

Laminate	nb of specimens	nb of onsets	nb of failures	average stress (Mpa)	(Mpa)
$[\pm 10]_s$	5	3	3	826	27
$[\pm 10_2]_s$	5	0	5	722	28
$[\pm 10_3]_s$	5	0	5	655	26
$[\pm 10_4]_s$	4	2	1	580	27
$[\pm 10_5]_s$	5	0	5	619	16
$[\pm 10_8]_s$	5	4	1	447	25
$[\pm 20]_s$	5	3	0	599	16
$[\pm 20_2]_s$	5	1	4	495	26
$[\pm 20_3]_s$	5	1	4	418	15
$[\pm 20_4]_s$	5	0	5	394	14
$[\pm 20_5]_s$	5	1	4	354	22
$[\pm 30]_s$	4	3	1	406	14
$[\pm 30_2]_s$	4	3	1	304	7
$[\pm 30_3]_s$	4	2	2	269	2
$[\pm 30_4]_s$	5	2	3	232	8
$[\pm 30_5]_s$	5	1	4	227	15
$[\pm 25/90_{1/2}]_s$	5	4	0	405	34
$[\pm 25_2/90]_s$	5	5	0	347	28
$[\pm 25_3/90_{3/2}]_s$	5	5	0	264	22
$[\pm 25_4/90_2]_s$	5	5	0	215	17
$[\pm 25_5/90_{5/2}]_s$	3	3	0	171	4
$[15_2/90/-15_2]_s$	3	2	1	484	12
$[15_4/90_2/-15_4]_s$	3	0	3	333	14
$[15_6/90_3/-15_6]_s$	5	2	3	271	12
$[15_8/90_4/-15_8]_s$	5	2	3	229	4
$[15_{10}/90_5/-15_{10}]_s$	5	2	3	204	4
$[30_4/90_2/-30_4]_s$	5	2	3	209	12

table 3 :tests results

Delamination type (onset or failure) is given. Except for the $[\pm 25_2/90]_s$, the failure stress is very close to the delamination onset stress. When no onset was detected, the failure stress has been used.

ANALYSIS

Classical laminate theory is an efficient approach for the study of laminates. Its basic assumptions provide fast and good results, owing to the fact that thickness is small compared with others dimensions. However, the boundary conditions are not accurate enough to show edge effects.

Stress calculation

Lecuyer [2] achieved an interlaminar stress calculation using appropriate boundary conditions and an asymptotic method. Applied to a linear elastic behaviour laminate, it provides the exact full stress tensor on a bidimensional domain.

Fig. 7

It consists of adding a tensor to the laminate solution to make the full solution resolve the true boundary conditions. The calculation uses a finite element method in the thickness direction (z) and solves an eigen value problem in the direction normal to the edge (y). The solution can be expressed quasi-analytically by the following expression :

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N a_k e^{-\lambda_k \frac{y}{h}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} is the stress at a given z location,

h is the laminate thickness,

a_k is related to the eigen vector corresponding to the eigen value λ_k ; none of them depends of h ,

N is related to the number of nodes in the finite element mesh.

The dependence of σ_{ij} to h is explicit.

The out of plane stresses can be singular at the edge of the laminates.

Criterion

The following expression was used as stress criterion :

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}}{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D} + \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^2 + \bar{\sigma}_{yz}^2}{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D} \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

It is supposed that only interlaminar stresses act in the delamination process.

A critical length, y_0 , is used to take the average stress on this distance. It stands for the distance on which the micro-damages occur, where the stress is redistributed. It is supposed to be characteristic of the interlaminar material (eg resin, fibres and their orientations in adjacent plies) [1].

There are two critical lengths, y_{0xz} and y_{0zz} , which correspond to interlaminar shear and interlaminar tension modes.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{zz} = \frac{1}{y_{0zz}} \int_0^{y_{0zz}} \sigma_{zz} dy \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{iz} = \frac{1}{y_{0xz}} \int_0^{y_{0xz}} \sigma_{iz} dy \quad (4)$$

where i can be x or y.

Parameters identification

Parameters $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D$, $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D$, y_{0zz} et y_{0xz} have to be found from appropriate test results. Each term (tension or shear) is studied separately and associated parameters are identified from specific test results.

- interlaminar xz shear :

$[\pm\theta_n]_s$ specimens ($5^\circ < \theta < 35^\circ$) delaminate under interlaminar xz shear stress [3]. Delamination occurs between $+\theta$ and $-\theta$ layers. The criterion can be written :

$$\frac{|\bar{\sigma}_{xz}|}{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D} \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

Eqn 1, 4 et 5 give the delamination onset :

$$\frac{1}{y_{0xz}} \int_0^{y_{0xz}} \sum_{k=1}^N a_k e^{-\lambda_k \frac{y}{h}} = \bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D \quad (6)$$

and $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D$ doesn't depend on y_{0xz} nor h .

Hence the curves plotting $\frac{1}{y_{0xz}} \int_0^{y_{0xz}} \sum_{k=1}^N a_k e^{-\lambda_k \frac{y}{h}}$ versus y_{0xz} and for various h (specimens of various thicknesses were tested) must intersect in one point. Edge delamination tests give the applied stress at the delamination onset, and allows the calculation of the left term in Eqn. 6. Fig. 8 shows these curve for a $[\pm 30]_s$ laminate.

This figure shows how it is difficult to have one intersection point because of dispersion on test results. A least square method was used to avoid such uncertainties.

fig 8 : identification for a $[\pm 30]_s$

- interlaminar tension

$[\pm 25_n/90_{n/2}]_s$ laminates can exhibit delamination in the middle of the 90° ply under tension only [4]. The criterion becomes :

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}}{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D} \leq 1 \quad (7)$$

The same method than for the shear term could be used to identify the corresponding parameters. However here, the delamination occurs in the middle of the 90° ply. It has been shown that this kind of "interface" has different properties than θ_1/θ_2 interface [5]. No stacking sequence has been found (does it exist?) to make interlaminar tension without shear at a θ_1/θ_2 interface. In order to identify the tension parameters $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D$ and y_{0zz} , specimens under interlaminar tension and shear have been tested.

- interlaminar tension and shear

$[15_{2n}/90_n/-15_{2n}]_s$ EDT specimens under tension exhibit interlaminar tension and shear. The tension term of the criterion can be related to shear terms, whose parameters are supposed to be known :

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}}{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D} \leq 1 - \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^2 + \bar{\sigma}_{yz}^2}{\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D{}^2} \quad (8)$$

The method described can be applied to identify the tension parameters $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D$ y_{0zz} . This process adds the uncertainties of the shear identification to the tension one.

RESULTS

Shear

Tests on $[\pm\theta]_s$, $\theta=10, 20$ et 30° , have been made to learn whether the parameters $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D$ and y_{0xz} depend on θ . Their value identified once with the three sets of experimental results are : $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D = 160$ Mpa and $y_{0xz} = 0.06$ mm. Figure 9 shows the model prediction with these parameters.

Fig. 9 : model and tests results, $[\pm\theta]_s$, $\theta=10, 20$ et 30°

The theoretical curves give a good approximation of the results of the tests.

combined mode

The identification of the tension parameters $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D$ and y_{0zz} gives unreasonable values. A quick conclusion is to say that the criterion is unable to give good results for these laminates, owing to the laminate or the criterion itself. However, a comparison has been made between the results of the tests and predictions of the criterion with the following parameters : $\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^D = 50$ Mpa, which corresponds to the intralaminar transverse strength, and $y_{0zz} = 0.060$ mm, the same as shear critical length. It is interesting to note, on fig. 10, that the variations of this theoretical curve versus the thickness are similar to those of test results, with an offset of 350 MPa. Note that a classical criterion gives a constant value whatever the thickness. This remark allows one to think that it is possible to reproduce the test results by the use of edge stresses. It may be necessary to apply a full criterion (intra and interlaminar). This point could be confirmed by the inclination of traverse cracks in 90° plies of $[\pm 25_n/90_{n/2}]_s$.

Fig. 10 : model and tests results, $[15_2/90/-15_2]_s$

CONCLUSION

Onset delamination stresses on different stacking sequences are available. Edge delamination specimens exhibit different failure behaviour : unstable ($[\pm\theta]_s$, $\theta=10, 20$ et 30°), stable ($[\pm 25_n/90_{n/2}]_s$) or unstable after a small onset ($[15_2/90/-15_2]_s$).

The criterion provides a good prediction of the results of the tests for interlaminar shear.

Parameters values $\bar{\sigma}_{xz}^D = 160$ Mpa and $y_{0xz} = 0.08$ mm have been identified on the three sets of results ($[\pm\theta]_s$, $\theta=10, 20$ et 30°).

Identification of the tension parameters based on results of tests on $[15_2/90/-15_2]_s$ laminates gives bad results. However, it seems important to take into account the edge effect, and the influence of the thickness of specimens. A full criterion is to be tested.

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